

Effects of Sodium Alkyl Sulfates on Polarographic Waves

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The effects of adsorbed layers of sodium alkyl sulfates of various chain lengths on the polarographic reduction waves of positive, negative, and neutral complexes of copper have been studied. Positive and neutral complexes are similarly affected. The reduction of negative complexes is strongly hindered by the adsorbed layers. The extent of surface coverage of the dodecyl and tetradecyl sulfates was estimated from current-time curves and Koryta's equation.

THE sodium alkyl sulfates exhibit strong surface active properties in water. Their effectiveness in suppressing polarographic maxima has recently been studied in detail.¹ These compounds, in addition to suppressing maxima, also distort polarographic waves, eliminate them completely, or shift the half wave potentials.² The inhibiting or distorting effects of the surfactants on the polarographic waves are due to their strong adsorption on the mercury surface of the DME.³ The effect of the sodium dodecyl sulfate on the reduction waves of positively charged complexes of triethylenetetramine (trien) and tetraethylenepentamine (tetren) has been studied by conventional polarography.^{4,5} Since the effects of other members of the homologous series (octyl through octadecyl) have not been reported in the literature, this investigation was made to study their effects on the polarographic waves of positive, neutral and negative complexes of copper. The effects were investigated by means of current-voltage and current-time curves.

Experimental

A Sargent Model XV Polarograph was used to obtain all current-voltage curves. The current-time curves were obtained at constant applied potential using a slidewire potentiometer. The cell current was displayed on the *y*-axis of a Tektronix Model 502A oscilloscope by using the voltage drop across a 174 ohm resistor connected in series with the polarographic cell. All potentials reported are referred to the saturated calomel electrode (SCE), and the temperature was $25 \pm 1^\circ$ unless otherwise noted. Details with respect to the type and cleaning of the cells used, the deaeration procedure, and the elimination of noise from the signals, are the same as reported earlier.¹

The sodium alkyl sulfates, octyl (C_8), through octadecyl (C_{18}), were obtained from the Procter and Gamble Company and freshly prepared solutions of these were used for each experiment. Triethyl-

enetetramine disulfate (trien, J. T. Baker, A. R. Grade) was used as received. Tetraethylenepentamine (tetren, Eastman, Technical Grade) was purified according to the procedure of Jonassen.⁵

Results and Discussion

Cu (tetren)²⁺ complex: A solution $8.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in tetren and $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ in Cu(II) in 0.16M acetate buffer of pH 4.50 yields a reversible⁵ wave at $-0.17v$. Although not observed by Jonassen et al.⁵, there occurred a slight maximum which was very easily suppressed with all of the alkyl sulfates, excepting C_{18} ($5 \times 10^{-4}\%$ or less). Up to a concentration of about $5 \times 10^{-2}\%$ the C_8 - C_{14} alkyl sulfates caused no change in $E_{1/2}$ or the limiting current. The current-time curves were also unaffected. Above about $5 \times 10^{-2}\%$ of surfactant the upper part of the polarographic waves became drawn out. At these high concentrations the negatively charged adsorbed layer causes a decrease in the rate of electron transfer resulting in irreversibility. With the C_{16} and C_{18} alkyl sulfates, turbidity, erratic droptimes, and abrupt current fluctuations in the current-time curves were encountered. As well as could be determined, the $E_{1/2}$ values remained unchanged.

Cu (trien)²⁺ complex: As might be expected, the behavior of this complex was very similar to that of Cu (tetren)²⁺ in the same supporting electrolyte. The maximum was again easily suppressed ($1.1 \times 10^{-5} M$ for C_8 , and $1.7 \times 10^{-6} M$ for C_{12}). Irreversible behavior became apparent at the following concentrations: $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ C_8 , $1.8 \times 10^{-4} M$ C_{10} , and $5.2 \times 10^{-5} M$ C_{12} . Earlier workers⁵ indicated irreversible behavior for C_{12} at $3.5 \times 10^{-4} M$. We could not reach this concentration without the formation of a persistent turbidity at about $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ which resulted in erratic behavior. The C_{14} to C_{18} alkyl sulfates gave white precipitates in this electrolyte which also caused erratic behavior. The precipitates are undoubtedly the salts of trien and tetren with the alkyl sulfates since they will form in the absence of copper.

Cu (EDTA)²⁻ complex: The C_{12} alkyl sulfate is known to distort the reduction wave of the Cu

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(EDTA)²⁻ complex ion.⁴ In 0.1 *M* acetate buffer of pH 4.5 a sharp maximum is obtained. However, 1.0×10^{-3} *M* Cu(II) in 0.25 *M* EDTA at pH 4.32 gives a reversible wave at $E_3 = -0.32$ v. vs. SCE with no maximum.⁶ The latter conditions were used to avoid the maximum

On adding increasing amounts of C₈ to C₁₂ alkyl sulfates to this solution, the copper reduction wave splits into two parts yielding a "penetration" wave. In each case, well formed waves were obtained with the characteristics: alkyl sulfate, concentration at which penetration wave appears, $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of penetration wave; C₈, 3.91×10^{-3} *M*, -0.66 v.; C₁₀, 3.48×10^{-4} *M*, -0.72 v.; C₁₂, 1.62×10^{-4} *M*, -0.80 v. For the C₁₄ to C₁₈ alkyl sulfates, turbidity and wild current fluctuations were obtained in each case.

Figure 1 depicts the behavior with C₁₄. The fluctuations were worse with C₁₈ and C₁₅. Formation of the penetration wave is apparent, but the E_3 values cannot be accurately determined although it is evidently more negative than -0.8 v. Turbidity and erratic behavior commenced at the following concentrations: C₁₄, 7.59×10^{-5} *M* (0.0024%); C₁₅, 5.69×10^{-5} *M* (0.00196%); C₁₈, 3.98×10^{-5} *M* (0.0014%).

The formation of penetration waves has been attributed to similarity of charge between the alkyl sulfate and the copper—EDTA complex ion.⁷ As the surface of the DME becomes covered with the alkyl sulfate the accumulated negative charge repels the depolarizer. Thus, the Cu(EDTA)²⁻ ions must cross an energy barrier before reduction can occur; as a result, the reduction wave is shifted to more negative potentials. The shift increases in the order, C₈ < C₁₀ < C₁₂ < C₁₄, which is the order of the series as evidenced by electrocapillary measurements.¹

Confirmatory evidence as to the validity of this conclusion was sought by a study of the variation of the current at constant potential during the lifetime of single drops. The inhibition of the current by the surface active substance during the lifetime of a drop may be related to the extent of coverage of the drop surface by the adsorbed species.²

Figures 2, 3a, 3b, 4, 5a and 5b are current-time curves of 1.0×10^{-3} *M* Cu (II) in 0.25 *M* EDTA at pH 4.32. The applied potential was set at -0.60 v. in all cases. This is well up on the diffusion current plateau for the reduction of the Cu(EDTA)²⁻ complex ion (Fig. 1).

The behavior of C₁₂ alkyl sulfate shown in Figure 4 is similar to the curves obtained by Schmid and Reilley² for Triton X-100 and eosin. It is seen that the curves are identical during the early part of the drop life. This is because the rate at which the surfactant covers the drop is diffusion controlled, and not enough C₁₂ alkyl sulfate has been adsorbed to retard the electrode reaction appreciably. Later on, the current decreases as the surfactant covers a larger and larger fraction of the surface of the growing drop. Eventually, the current drops to zero when the drop surface is completely covered by a monolayer of surfactant. This occurs in shorter time as the concentration of surfactant is increased.

The dependence of the time required to reach complete surface coverage on the bulk concentration of adsorbed species has been studied by Koryta.⁸

Fig. 1. Effect on sodium tetradecyl sulfate on the reduction of Cu-EDTA complex. Polarograms of a solution containing 1×10^{-3} *M* Cu(II) in 0.25 *M* EDTA, pH 4.32 with various amounts of sodium tetradecyl sulfate present: (1) 0; (2) 3.13×10^{-3} *M*; (3) 6.20×10^{-3} *M*; (4) 7.59×10^{-3} *M*; (5) 4.74×10^{-3} *M*.

It is assumed in equation [1] that the adsorption coefficient is so large that all of the surface active species are adsorbed immediately on reaching the drop surface. Thus, diffusion is the rate controlling process.

$$\theta = 1.82 \times 10^6 \Gamma_s^2 / DC^2 \quad \dots [1]$$

In this equation θ is the time (sec) required for complete coverage of the drop, Γ_s is the maximum moles of adsorbed species per cm² of mercury surface, D is the diffusion coefficient (cm²/sec) of the species adsorbed, and C is its bulk concentration (moles/l).

Fig. 2-5: Current-time curves for a solution containing 1×10^{-3} *M* Cu(II), 0.25 *M* EDTA, pH 4.32 with various amounts of sodium alkyl sulfates present.

Fig. 2. (A) 0; (B) 0.392; (C) 1.66; (D) 2.44; (E) 3.92; (F) 5.62×10^{-3} *M* sodium octyl sulfate.

Fig. 3a. (A) 0.38; (B) 0.753; (C) 1.48; (D) $2.17 \times 10^{-4} M$ sodium decyl sulfate.

Fig. 3b. (E) 2.68; (F) $3.49 \times 10^{-4} M$ sodium decyl sulfate.

Fig. 4. (A) 0; (B) 0.343; (C) 0.678; (D) 1.07; (E) 1.64; (F) 1.91; (G) $2.41 \times 10^{-4} M$ sodium dodecyl sulfate.

If the time θ in equation [1] may be replaced by t° , the time required for the current to reach zero, than a plot of t° vs. $1/C^2$ should be a straight line passing through the origin. Such a plot is shown

in Fig. 6 for the data on C_{12} alkyl sulfate (Fig. 4) and on C_{14} alkyl sulfate (Fig. 5a and 5b). Koryta's equation is apparently followed in these two instances.

Fig. 5a. (1) 0; (2) 0.313; (3) 0.921; (4) $1.50 \times 10^{-4} M$ sodium tetradecyl sulfate.

Fig. 5b. (5) 2.41; (6) 2.88; (7) $4.70 \times 10^{-4} M$ sodium tetradecyl sulfate.

Fig. 6. t° vs $1/C^2$ plot based on Koryta's equation in case of (1) sodium dodecyl sulfate; (2) sodium tetradecyl sulfate.

It was of interest for comparative purposes to obtain an approximate value for Γ_s from these data. To do so, the diffusion coefficient of the $C_{12}H_{25}SO_4^-$ ion is needed. No literature value could be found, but apparent diffusion coefficients of partially micellized solutions of C_{12} alkyl sulfate have been measured by Courchene⁹ at 30°. From his data we obtained a value of 6.2×10^{-6} cm²/sec for the monomeric ion. On correction to 25° the value of D_0 was estimated at 4.8×10^{-6} cm²/sec. Using this and the slope of the Koryta plot, we obtain 2.3×10^{-10} mole/cm² for Γ_s .

No data on the diffusion coefficient of the C_{14} alkyl sulfate could be found. Assuming it to be the same as the C_{12} alkyl sulfate, we calculated Γ_s for C_{14} alkyl sulfate to be 4.5×10^{-10} mole/cm². This clearly indicates more effective adsorption of C_{14} over C_{12} alkyl sulfate since D for the C_{14} compound would be expected to be smaller than D for C_{12} .

These values are of the same magnitude as those obtained for eosin² ($\Gamma_s = 1.46 \times 10^{-10}$ mole/cm²) and Triton X-100²⁷ ($\Gamma_s = 0.96 \times 10^{-10}$ mole/cm²), two widely used polarographic maximum suppressors.

The current-time curves showing the effect of the C_8 alkyl sulfate on the Cu-EDTA system (Fig. 2) were observed to be similar to those obtained using thymol on Cu(EDTA)²⁻ in 0.1 M acetate buffer². Like thymol, the C_8 alkyl sulfate has weak surface active properties and decreases the diffusion current only when present at relatively high concentrations. However, as the concentration of C_8 alkyl sulfate is increased, the shape of the curve deviates from the normal one-sixth order parabola. Unlike the behavior of C_{12} alkyl sulfate, this deviation occurs almost from the start of the drop formation. This type of behavior has been explained by Schmid and Reilley². In this case, the diffusion coefficient of the C_8 alkyl sulfate should be larger than that of the C_{12} compound. Furthermore, its concentration is much higher. Consequently, the time required for complete coverage of the drop surface with a monolayer is very small (less than a millisecond). As a result, the process altering the shape of the current-time curves cannot be diffusion controlled. Instead, the mercury drop is almost instantly covered with an equilibrium concentration of the C_8 compound, and the fraction of the surface covered remains constant throughout the lifetime of the drop.

Current-time curves for the C_{10} alkyl sulfate are shown in Fig. 3a and 3b, and its behavior is seen to be intermediate between that of C_8 and C_{12} . The shape of the curve in the early part of the drop life is probably controlled by the rate at which the C_{10} alkyl sulfate is adsorbed at the mercury surface. Later, an equilibrium surface coverage (less than 100%) is reached and the curve shape becomes similar to that observed with the C_8 compound. The same behavior was indicated by electrocapillary measurements.¹

As was mentioned earlier, the addition of C_{14} , C_{16} and C_{18} alkyl sulfates to the Cu-EDTA solutions results in slightly turbid solutions and erratic behavior

in the region of the limiting current plateau. Current-time curves for the C_{14} alkyl sulfate are shown in Fig. 5a and 5b. The general shape of these curves was reproducible and the i° vs. $1/C^2$ plot was linear. The sharp current spikes were erratic, and the curves illustrated may only be regarded as typical. It is tempting to speculate that these are caused by "cracks" developing in a firmly attached adsorption layer as the mercury drop expands. The current-time curves obtained with C_{16} and C_{18} alkyl sulfate present were so erratic that little could be done with them.

Cu (tart)^o complex: The effects of gelatin and Triton X-100 on the reduction was of this neutral complex ion have been previously studied.² Gelatin was found to cause a slight depression and Triton X-100 a strong depression of the limiting current.

The current-voltage curve obtained with 1.0×10^{-3} M Cu (II) in 0.10 M tartrate buffer at pH 4.0 showed a very large, sharp-breaking maximum (break-off potential = -0.40v.). The break-off potential shifted in the positive direction as alkyl sulfates were added (e.g., for C_8 alkyl sulfate concentration C_8 , break-off potential; 2.15×10^{-5} M, -0.36v.; 1.08×10^{-4} M, -0.24v.; 3.62×10^{-4} M, -0.14v.; maximum suppression point = 1.03×10^{-3} M). After suppression of the maximum, further additions of C_8 - C_{14} alkyl sulfates had no effect on the half wave potential which remained at -0.05v. Furthermore, up to the largest concentration tested (C_8 , 1.03×10^{-2} M; C_{10} , 1.91×10^{-3} M; C_{12} , 3.14×10^{-4} M; C_{14} , 2.87×10^{-4} M) the limiting current was also unaffected. Accordingly, for this neutral complex penetration of the adsorbed layer of surfactant proceeds without difficulty. Also, as in the case of the positively charged complexes, slight irreversibility was observed at higher surfactant concentrations.

Under condition where the supply of depolarizer to the DME is diffusion controlled, the effects of the presence of alkyl sulfates may be summarized as follows:

(1) Low concentrations of alkyl sulfates, such as are commonly used for the suppression of polarographic maxima, have no effect on the half wave potential or the limiting current for the reduction of positively charged complex ions. Larger concentrations may cause irreversible behavior. The concentration of alkyl sulfate at which irreversibility becomes apparent decreases with increasing length of the alkyl chain.

(2) When negatively charged complexes are reduced in the presence of the negatively charged alkyl sulfates, large shifts in the half wave potential result. This indicates the establishment of an energy barrier towards reduction by the adsorbed layer of alkyl sulfate on the mercury surface. This effect is also more pronounced the longer the chain length. As a result, these surfactants should not be used in analytical methods involving the reduction of anions.

(3) Alkyl sulfates affect the reduction waves of neutral complexes in much the same way as cationic complexes.

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References

1. V. KUMAR and T. W. GILBERT, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1972, **40**, 419.
2. R. W. SCHMID and C. N. REILLEY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 2087.
3. L. MEITES and T. MEITES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 177.
4. E. JACOBSEN and G. KALLAND, *Anal. Chem. Acta.*, 1964, **30**, 240.
5. HANS B. JONASSEN, J. A. BERTAND, F. R. GROVES JR. and R. I. STEARNS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4279.
6. R. L. PECOK, *Anal. Chem.*, 1953, **25**, 561.
7. R. G. BARRADAS and F. M. KIMMERLE, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1966, **11**, 163.
8. J. KORYTA, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, **18**, 206.
9. W. L. COURCHENE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 1870.